

Organic Derivatives of Zirconium : Part I. Reactions with Bidentate Ligands

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Acetylacetone reacts with zirconium isopropoxide in different molar ratios to give $Zr(OPr^i)_3(acac)$, $(Pr^iOH)I$, $Zr(OPr^i)_2(acac)_2II$, and $Zr(OPr^i)(acac)_3$, IIIa. Reactions have also been studied with methyl acetoacetate, phenyl salicylate and benzoylacetone and the compounds IIb, IIc and IIId respectively have been isolated.

Chelate compounds of zirconium have also been prepared with bidentate ligand 2-methylpentane-2, 4-diol having composition $Zr(OR)_2(O_2C_6H_{12})(IV)$, $Zr(O_2C_6H_{12})_2(V)$, $Zr(O_2C_6H_{12})(O_2C_6H_{13})_2(VI)$.

Molecular weights of the compounds III and VI have been determined in boiling benzene. Attempts to prepare $Zr(acac)_4$ by the reaction of $Zr(OPr^i)(acac)_3$ and $Zr(OPr^i)_4(Pr^iOH)$ with the excess of the ligand were unsuccessful.

Reactions of zirconium tetrachloride with acetylacetone have been studied quite in detail¹⁻⁵. It has been shown that zirconium tetrachloride reacts with acetylacetone in benzene to give only $Zr(acac)_3Cl$ and not $Zr(acac)_4$. Compounds $Zr(acac)_2Cl_2$ and $Zr(acac)Cl_3$ have also been reported. Adducts of zirconium tetrachloride with acetylacetone⁶ have been shown to have the composition $ZrCl_4 \cdot acacH$. Much work has also been done on the reactions of zirconium alkoxides with higher alcohols^{7,8}, in which higher alcohols replace lower ones.

In view of the above study, it was of interest to investigate the reactions between zirconium isopropoxides and acetylacetone which have not been studied so far.

Further, in view of the study of glycol derivatives of Si^9 , Ge^{10} , Sn^{11} , Ti^{12-14} , it seemed worthwhile to investigate the reactions between zirconium isopropoxide and 2-methylpentane-2, 4-diol.

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In the present study, the reactions of zirconium isopropoxide with various molar ratios of acetylacetone and 2-methyl pentane-2, 4-diol were carried out and the reaction products were isolated in pure state and analysed. It was found that the reaction of zirconium isopropoxide with 2-methylpentane-2, 4-diol are similar to those described for titanium.¹⁴

The reactions have been followed by estimating the isopropanol produced in the reactions after their removal azeotropically with benzene.

The results obtained can be represented schematically as :

Compounds $\text{Zr}(\text{acac})_3(\text{OPr}^i)$, IIIa; $\text{Zr}(\text{acac})_2(\text{OPr}^i)_2$, II; and $\text{Zr}(\text{acac})(\text{OPr}^i)_3 \cdot (\text{Pr}^i\text{OH})$, I; have been obtained. With the excess of the ligand, tetra-acetylacetonate derivative was not obtained. Molecular complexity of the compound IIIa in boiling benzene was found to be 1.06 which shows that zirconium has coordination number seven and is in conformity with the results already obtained in case of $\text{Zr}(\text{acac})_3\text{Cl}$.^{4,5} Compound II is a monomer in refluxing benzene, showing a coordinate valency of six for zirconium.

Reactions of zirconium isopropoxide have also been studied with methyl acetoacetate, phenyl salicylate and benzoylacetone, in excess of the reagents. The compounds obtained, were similar to the one obtained in the case of acetylacetone. Molecular weights of the compounds have been determined in boiling benzene and they have been found to be monomer, (Table I).

TABLE I

S.No.	Reactants	Amounts (g)	Product, state and yield in gms.	% Zr		Analysis Alcohol in azeotrope (g.)		Molecular Wt.	
				Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
1.	$Zr(OPr^t)_4$, (Pr ^t OH) Acetylacetone	1.19 0.30	$Zr(OPr^t)_3(acac)$, Pr ^t OH Light yellow sticky cryst. (1.13)	21.60	21.31	0.17	0.18		
2.	$Zr(OPr^t)_4$, (Pr ^t OH) Acetylacetone	1.03 0.61	$Zr(OPr^t)_2(acac)$ Light yellow crystals (0.60)	22.50	22.36	0.41	0.47	413	417
3.	$Zr(OPr^t)_4$, (Pr ^t OH) Acetylacetone	1.07 0.85	$Zr(OPr^t)(acac)_3$ Light yellow solid (1.22)	20.54	20.35	0.64	0.65	477	447
4.	$Zr(OPr^t)_4$, (Pr ^t OH) Acetylacetone	0.55 1.55	Light yellow solid $Zr(OPr^t)(acac)_3$	20.36	20.35	0.36	0.33	474	447
5.	$Zr(OPr^t)_4$, (Pr ^t OH) Methylacetacetate	0.70 1.16	$Zr(OPr^t)(meac)_3$ Cream coloured crystalline solid(1.23)	18.45	18.05	0.41	0.42	530	495
6.	$Zr(OPr^t)_4$, (Pr ^t OH) Phenylsalicylate	0.79 1.75	$Zr(OPr^t)(Phsal)_3$ White crystalline solid (1.49)	11.29	11.52	0.50	0.48	806	789
7.	$Zr(OPr^t)_4$, (Pr ^t OH) Benzoylacetone	0.44 0.75	$Zr(OPr^t)(Bzac)_3$ Light yellow crystalline solid (0.48)	14.22	14.37	0.25	0.27	709	633

TABLE II

Reactants	Products and yield in gms.	Analysis			
		% zirconium		Amount of alcohol in gms.	
		Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
1. $Zr(OPr)_4(Pr^iOH)$ Benzene 2-methylpentane-2, 4-diol	2.1 g. 35 ml. 0.68 g.				
	$Zr(OC_3H_7)_2(C_6H_{12}O_2)$ White foamy solid (1.71 g.) m.p. 85°	28.07	28.00	0.9606	0.9768
2. $Zr(OPr)_4(Pr^iOH)$ Benzene 2-methylpentane-2, 4-diol	2.18 g. 40 ml. 1.33 g.				
	$Zr(C_6H_{12}O_2)$ White solid (1.98 g.) Decomposes above 300°	28.18	28.12	1.62	1.69
3. $Zr(OPr)_4(Pr^iOH)$ Benzene 2-methylpentane-2, 4-diol	1.93 g. 30 ml. 1.81 g.				
	$Zr(C_6H_{12}O_2)(C_6H_{13}O_2)_2$ White crystalline solid (2.24 g.) m.p. 170°	20.69	20.64	—	—
4. $Zr(OPr)_4(Pr^iOH)$ Benzene 2-methylpentane-2, 4-diol	2.05 g. 30 ml. 3.80g.				
	$Zr(C_6H_{12}O_2)(C_6H_{13}O_2)_2$ White crystalline solid (1.648) m.p. 171°	20.75	20.64	1.53	1.59
5. $Zr(C_6H_{12}O_2)_2$ Benzene 2-methylpentane-2, 4-diol	0.99g. 25 ml. 0.36g.				
	$Zr(C_6H_{12}O_2)(C_6H_{13}O_2)_2$ White crystalline solid (1.37) m.p. 170°	20.79	20.64	—	—

Compound (VI) in boiling benzene was found to be monomer with the possible structure as VI in which zirconium may attain coordination number six.

EXPERIMENTAL

Apparatus: Apparatus with interchangeable joints have been used¹⁵. Care was taken to ensure that both reagents and apparatus were moisture free. Molecular weights were determined by means of Gallankamp semi-micro ebulliometer.

Materials: Zirconium isopropoxide was prepared as in literature⁷ and was analysed before use. Acetylacetone, benzoylacetone, methyl acetoacetate and 2-methyl pentane-2, 4-diol (all BDH) were used after distillation. Phenyl salicylate was used after drying under reduced pressure at 25°. Benzene (BDH) was dried and purified as usual¹⁵.

Analytical Methods: Zirconium was estimated gravimetrically and isopropanol oxidimetrically according to the method described earlier⁸.

Reactions

1. *Reaction between zirconium isopropoxide and acetylacetone in the molar ratios of 1,2,3 and in excess in benzene*: Zirconium isopropoxide (1 mole) was taken in benzene and to this was added acetylacetone in the molar ratios of 1,2,3 and in excess. In each case no heat was produced on shaking and no colour change was visible. The reaction mixture was refluxed for about 1½ hours and then the azeotrope was taken in about 2 hrs time at the fractionating column. The excess of the benzene was distilled out and the mixture was allowed to stay overnight. In some cases, crystals were obtained which were dried under reduced pressure after removing the solvent. In other cases the last traces of the solvent were removed under vacuum and the solid compound was obtained. Table I; 1-4.

Zirconium isopropoxide and acetylacetone was also mixed in different ratios in benzene without refluxing and only keeping overnight. It was observed that after removing benzene, the analysis of the compound obtained corresponded to that of zirconium isopropoxide.

2. *Reaction between zirconium mono-isopropoxy tris-acetylacetonate and excess acetylacetone in benzene (an attempt to prepare zirconium tetraacetylacetonate)*: Acetylacetone (1.19 g.) was added to a solution of freshly prepared zirconium monoisopropoxy tris-acetylacetonate (1.22 g.) in benzene. No heat was produced. After refluxing the reaction mixture for about 2 hrs, the distilling liquid was removed in about 6 hrs. at 78-79°. No alcohol in the distilling liquid was found. The solid compound, obtained after drying under vacuum, gave the analysis as: Found: Zr, 20.35, Required for $Zr(OPr^i)(acac)_3$; Zr, 20.35%.

3. *Reaction between zirconium isopropoxide and excess (more than 4 mols) of methyl acetoacetate, phenyl salicylate or benzoylacetone in benzene*: To a solution of zirconium isopropoxide in benzene excess of the reagent (4 mols) was added. The reaction mixture on shaking became very slightly hot. It was refluxed for about 1½ hours and then the azeotrope was taken at the fractionating column. The excess of benzene was also distilled out. The reaction mixture was kept overnight when crystals were deposited which were filtered and washed with dry benzene and were dried under vacuum at 30°. Table I, 5-7.

4. *Reactions between zirconium isopropoxide and 2-methylpentane-2, 4-diol in different ratios in benzene*: To zirconium isopropoxide in benzene was added 2-methylpentane-2, 4-diol. The mixture became warm on shaking. After refluxing for about 2 hrs and taking azeotrope, the excess of the benzene was distilled out. On cooling a clear solution was obtained from which the last traces of benzene were removed under vacuum (80° and 1 mm pressure). White solid compounds were obtained in all cases. The properties of the compounds and analysis are given in the table II; 1-4.

5. *Reaction between zirconium diglycollate II and 2-methylpentane-2, 4-diol in the molar ratio of 1 : 1 in benzene*: To the compound II in benzene was added 2-methylpentane-2, 4-diol and the mixture was shaken and refluxed. Some benzene was distilled over. On cooling, white crystalline solid separated out. The properties and analysis are given in the table II; 5.

The author is thankful to Prof. R. C. Mehrotra for valuable suggestions in this work.